

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and
Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

The first hackathon organised
Milestone M5.2

ESiWACE3 Milestone M5.2

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Contact details

Project Office: esiwace3@bsc.es

Website: www.esiwace.eu

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/esiwace>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@esiwace880>

LinkedIn:

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/esiwace3>

Vimeo: <https://www.vimeo.com/esiwace>

ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results

<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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ESiWACE3 Milestone M5.2

European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Lead Beneficiary:

CSC-Tieteen Tietotekniikan Keskus OY (CSC), Jarmo Mäkelä, Tuomas Lunttila, Tuomas Rossi, Aurélie Vancraeynest, Emanuele Vitali, Ulf Tigferstedt

Other contributing authors:

Eviden, Loris Lucido

Stichting Netherlands e-Science Center (NLeSC), Victor Azizi, Stijn Heldens

Type:

Dissemination level:

PU (for public use)

Delivery date:

Due date in month 11. Actually delivery date 23 November 2023

Means of verifications:

Web page of the hackathon demonstrates that it has been organised.

Achieved:

Yes

If not achieved, indicate forecast achievement date:

-

Comments:

The lead beneficiary was changed from NLeSC to CSC due to change in venue. First hackathon was initially planned to be held in Netherlands but was changed to Finland to ease the scheduling pressure on all training events.

The ESiWACE3 hackathon was organised in tangent with eFlows4HPC workshop to foster collaboration and knowledge transfer. The hackathon call¹, event page² as well as a collated feedback report³ are available for public viewing.

¹ <https://ssl.eventilla.com/event/N47aZ>

² <https://siili.rahtiapp.fi/esiwace3-hackathon-oct-2023>

³ <https://ssl.eventilla.com/report/v3/102HNjme5EgAeyg/7de132eb-f108-4545-bb73-f809d8263d04>